

GUIDELINES ON FAST-TRACK RECOGNITION OF UKRAINIAN ACADEMIC QUALIFICATIONS

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FOREWORD

The Russian aggression of Ukraine launched on 24 February 2022 is forcing unprecedented numbers of people, mostly women and children, to flee their homes in search of shelter and safety in other European countries. These refugees face many serious challenges, including ensuring the education of children and young adults. The education authorities of the host countries are called upon to respond positively to a new and fast-moving reality, and to provide the necessary infrastructure, policies and measures to meet the Ukrainian refugee population's educational needs.

The European Commission is giving the highest priority to supporting the refugees as well as Member State authorities. Through the Erasmus+ Programme, the European Commission has been supporting the network of national recognition authorities to develop tools that help fair, transparent and fast recognition of qualifications. Thanks to the activation of the Temporary Protection directive the Ukrainian refugees have received the right to work and study in European Union. However, for this to happen, many people need their qualifications to be evaluated and recognised swiftly. Providing a simple and rapid recognition mechanism contributes greatly to ensuring that people enjoying temporary protection can study at an appropriate level, and work in jobs for which they are qualified.

The European Commission published a Recommendation on the recognition of academic and professional qualifications for people fleeing Russia's invasion of Ukraine. It provides Member States' authorities with guidance and practical advice to ensure a quick, fair and flexible recognition process of these qualifications. As Ukrainian refugees may have been forced to leave without their original documentation of qualifications, a flexible approach on how to assess recognition applications in such cases is essential, including reissuing diplomas in a digital format. The European Commission has taken forward the implementation of this Recommendation through organising a Webinar "Online training for fast-track recognition of Ukrainian academic qualifications", together with CIMEA, the Italian national recognition information centre, which addressed the different challenges authorities are facing.

To further help, Commissioner Gabriel proposed to apply flexibility with the on-going Erasmus+ projects to support students and academics from Ukraine. The Commission has also announced flexibility for Regional Funds, and the Recovery and Resilience facility programmes to re-purpose some of the funds for helping Ukraine.

INTRODUCTION

This document has been prepared with the aim of providing concrete support to higher education institutions in the evaluation of Ukrainian qualifications, thus helping to make the most of the skills, knowledge and abilities of the title holders.

The document, divided into four parts, explores the structure of the Ukrainian scholastic and higher education system, focusing first on the resources available, and then describing in greater detail the subdivision of the study cycles and the qualifications awarded.

The documentation issued and the diplomas released for the main qualifications of this system are also presented, thereby providing guidelines to aid in their interpretation and facilitate the elimination of the language barrier faced in verifying the elements of a single qualification.

The main methods of verifying the authenticity of qualifications are also described, in addition to the main information resources, not only including those already detailed in this document, but also other support resources for a more in-depth knowledge of the Ukrainian system and for a correct evaluation of its qualifications.

PART 1: THE UKRAINIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

1. AVAILABLE RESOURCES

1.1 ENIC-NARIC website

With a view to obtaining a reference information framework on the main characteristics of the Ukrainian scholastic and higher education system, the principal primary sources created and updated directly by the competent authorities of the country are listed below.

Ukraine is a signatory country to the Lisbon Convention and part of the Bologna Process. Ukraine is part of the ENIC (European National Information Centres) network of the Council of Europe and UNESCO.

In the Country Page¹ of the ENIC-NARIC website² dedicated to Ukraine, we can find official information about the following categories:

- 1 National Information Centres
- 2 National education bodies
- 3 School education system
- 4 Higher education
- 5 Quality Assurance in Higher Education
- 6 Post-secondary non-university education
- 7 Recognised higher education institutions
- 8 Policies and procedures for the recognition of qualifications
- 9 Recognition of Qualifications held by refugees
- 10 National Qualifications Framework
- 11 Diploma Supplement Information
- 12 Access to higher education
- 13 Verification sources to determine authenticity

Updating the information contained in the categories shown is performed directly by the Ukrainian authorities, and specifically by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (*Міністерство освіти і науки України*).

¹ <https://www.enic-naric.net/ukraine.aspx>

² <https://www.enic-naric.net/>

1.2 MoES Ukraine - Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine

The official website of the Ukrainian Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (MoES)³ provides the latest news on the national regulations and sector-wide changes (in English and Ukrainian). The information is arranged according to the key target groups who use the website - schoolchildren and parents, students and researchers, as well as educators and academic managers. The range of topics covered by MoES encompasses, i.e., the following:

- 1 Pre-school education
- 2 Extracurricular education
- 3 Inclusive education
- 4 Complete general secondary education
- 5 Vocational (vocational-technical) education
- 6 Professional pre-higher education
- 7 Higher and adult education
- 8 Digital transformation of education and science
- 9 Distance and online services

The dedicated page 'National Qualifications Framework'⁴ provides a comprehensive overview of all historic developments on Ukrainian NQF and the national qualifications system, including its various elements:

- action plans on NQF implementation in Ukraine and their monitoring;
- levels and descriptors of the NQF;
- legal-normative specifics on the national qualifications system;
- references to the National Qualifications Agency⁵;
- reports and analytical materials on NQF.

³ <https://mon.gov.ua/eng>

⁴ <http://mon.gov.ua/ua/tag/natsionalna-ramka-kvalifikatsiu>

⁵ <https://nqa.gov.ua/>

1.3 ENIC Ukraine - National Information Centre of Academic Mobility

On the website managed directly by the Ukrainian ENIC Centre⁶, available in three languages (Ukrainian, English and Russian), it is possible to find further information which expands upon the description of the school and higher education system of reference in more detail. In particular, it is possible to find:

- a description of the scholastic, vocational and higher education system;
- a list of the official higher education institutions;
- templates of final qualifications;
- the National Qualifications Framework (NQF);
- the online verification system for Apostilles⁷.

The National Qualifications Framework (NQF) was approved in Ukraine in 2011 and references Ukrainian qualifications both to the cycles of the Bologna Process (QF-EHEA) and to the levels of the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), including the so-called “vocational” titles, of a professional nature. Ukrainian NQF was self-referenced to the Qualifications Framework for the European Higher Education Area in 2021⁸, while the referencing process to the EQF is in process till the end of 2022.

⁶ <http://enic.in.ua/index.php/en/>

⁷ It should be noted that the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine is the body responsible for affixing the Apostille on academic documents with the involvement of the ENIC Ukraine Centre, the authenticity of documents is directly verified by the Centre itself.

⁸ Self-certification report on Compliance of the National Qualifications Framework Criteria and Procedures with the Qualifications Framework for the European Higher Education Area: <https://mon.gov.ua/storage/app/media/nrk/2021/11.10/01/Zvit.pro.samosertyfikatsiyu.NRK-EN-10.11-1.pdf>

A diagram of the Ukrainian NQF is shown below:

1.4 Q-Entry - International Database on Higher Education Entry Qualifications

The Q-ENTRY database is the result of an Erasmus+ project coordinated by CIMEA which aims to provide timely information on the final upper secondary qualifications of various countries that allow access to higher education courses. The Q-ENTRY database collects all upper secondary school qualifications that give access to higher education in 61 different systems.

The database is online and accessible free of charge and makes available, in a standardised format, all relevant information regarding the final scholastic qualifications listed, namely:

- name of the scholastic qualification in the original language;
- authorised awarding body;
- total years of schooling;
- entry requirements
- academic rights (for further study);
- format of the final diploma;
- useful resources.

This information is provided and updated directly by the competent national authorities and presented in English.

Q-ENTRY DB THE PROJECTS FAQ USER FEEDBACK

International Database on Higher Education Entry Qualifications

QUALIFICATIONS DETAILS

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Name of the qualification in original language	Атестат про загальну середню освіту from 01/01/ 2019: Свідоцтво про здобуття повної загальної середньої освіти
Translation in English	Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education
Awarding body	1. Ministry of Education and Science is responsible for the standard education 2. Regional Educational authorities are responsible for the licensing and attestation processes for the secondary educational institutions 3. Secondary educational institutions are responsible for the education process and issuance of certificates
Total number of years of schooling	11 years are required now for the secondary school graduation. Starting from 2018 the 12-year school system is being implemented (the first graduates of this system are expected in 12 years).
EQF level	The referencing of NQF to EQF is planned for the period of 2019-2020.
NQF level	3
Verification information	Ways of verification: - Infocurs Unified State Electronic Database in Education; - Apostille stamps and database of ENIC Ukraine of the issued apostille; - To inquire directly to educational institutions.
Useful links	Preschool and School Department of the Ministry of Education and Science in Ukraine Secondary Educational ENIC Ukraine National Information Centre of Academic Mobility Ukrainian Educational Quality Assurance Center (Center for External Independent Testing) Infocurs Unified State Electronic Database in Education (only in Ukrainian)

Comments/Additional Information

Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education gives general access to higher education. The state examination system, called External Independent Testing (EIT), provides equal access to higher education based on complete general secondary education.

Subjects are divided into 2 categories: 1. required fields (languages and literature, social science, art, mathematics, natural science, technologies, health and physical culture) and 2. optional fields (based on the specialization of a school).

Grading system: a 12-point scale, where 12 is the highest score and 1 is the lowest.

The school leaving certificate is issued on the unified template of the fixed sized with the usage of the photo and digital technologies.

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Update date of the records: 09/05/2019

2. SCHOOL AND TVET EDUCATION SYSTEM

2.1 Length of scholastic paths

Since the 1990s, numerous reforms have been introduced to change the Ukrainian school system. Below are the most significant ones, relating in particular to the modification of the overall years of schooling:

- until 1994, the total length of schooling in Ukraine was 10 years;
- from 1995 until today, the total length of schooling has been 11 years;
- since the last reform introduced in 2017 (*Про освіту*⁹, articles 3-4, comma 3, paragraph XII), the system has begun to gradually adopt a model based on 12 years of overall schooling. It should be noted that, according to forecasts, the first students who will complete the different school paths characterised by the new duration have completed or will finish the different phases of education on the following dates:
 - for primary education, on 1 September 2022
 - for lower secondary education, on 1 September 2027
 - for upper secondary education, on 1 September 2030.

Therefore, to date, the final upper secondary school qualifications are to be considered as composed of overall schooling of 11 years.

The current scholastic path, divided into classes ranging from Class 1 to Class 11, is defined as follows:

Vocational		Qualified worker	Up to 4 years (after Basic Secondary Education), up to 2 years (after Complete Secondary Education)	Access to the First Tertiary Level
General Secondary	Complete	Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education	2 years	Access to Vocational and to the First Tertiary Level
	Basic	Certificate of Basic General Secondary Education	5 years	Access to Vocational and Complete General Secondary Education
	Primary	-	4 years	Access to Basic General Secondary Education
Preschool				

⁹ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2145-19#Text>

Primary school is attended from the age of 6/7. This path lasts **four years** and covers **Classes 1 to 4**.

Basic **secondary school** has a **five-year duration** and covers **Classes 5 to 9**: upon completion of the ninth year of schooling, students take a **state exam** necessary to obtain the final qualification of basic **secondary school** called:

Certificate of Basic General Secondary Education

Свідоцтво про базову загальну середню освіту

If the students intend to continue their schooling, they can alternatively:

- continue their studies at upper secondary school for a further two years (Classes 10 and 11);
- opt for vocational and professional paths that lead to the award of *Junior Specialist Diploma/Диплом молодшого спеціаліста (last admission in 2019)*, *Professional Junior Bachelor Diploma/Диплом фахового молодшого бакалавра (first admission in 2020)* or *Qualified Worker Diploma/Диплом кваліфікованого робітника* qualifications¹⁰.

The **final secondary school qualification** has had two different names in Ukrainian:

From 1992 until 2018

Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education

Атестат про повну загальну середню освіту

As of 2019

Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education

Свідоцтво про здобуття повної загальної середньої освіти

These qualifications, with either name, allow access to higher education in Ukraine.

¹⁰ For an in-depth analysis of vocational qualifications, cf. Part 1, para 1.2 and Part 2, para 2.3 of this document.

Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education is issued after completion of the 11-year program and final exams of the State Final Attestation (the SFA) in several subjects (Mathematics and Ukrainian language – mandatory, and one-two subjects optional). The subjects and number of exams are specified annually by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine.

Since 2015, the SFA has been conducted in the form of the External Independent Evaluation (the EIE - more below). In this case, the results are added to the supplement of the Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education in the line for the SFA results. In certain cases, specified by the relevant legislation, graduates have the right to pass the SFA in another form provided by an educational institution or to be exempted from passing the SFA.

Together with the final diploma, an attachment is issued, called Addendum to the Certificate - Додаток до атестата/свідоцтва - containing the list of subjects studied during the last two years, the list of final exams taken for the SFA.

External Independent Evaluation – EIE / Зовнішнє незалежне оцінювання – ЗНО

The External Independent Evaluation (the EIE) is a component of the admission procedure to higher education programs as an instrument of competitive selection. The EIE ensures general secondary school graduates the right for equal and fair admission to higher education programs, as the EIE results are used to determine the competitive selection scores for different programs. Graduates choose subjects (3-5) for the EIE tests according to the list of chosen areas of study in higher education institutions. The results of the EIE in Ukraine are organised as rating scale: 100-200 points. The required subject groups and the EIE points for admission are specified by higher education institutions. Higher education institutions can also set additional conditions for admission (art and vocal exams, tests, interviews etc.). After the EIE tests, a Certificate of External Independent Evaluation and a separate Information Card with the results of the EIE are issued. The EIE certificates can be used to apply to higher education institutions for 2-3 years which is determined annually by the legal act governing the conditions of admission to higher education.

2.2 Exceptional measures adopted in reply to the pandemic emergency

The pandemic caused by the unexpected and sudden spread of COVID-19 has profoundly affected, from 2020 to today, the scholastic and higher education sector on a global scale. In order to monitor the actions taken at national level by individual countries to ensure the completion of scholastic and higher education cycles during the pandemic, the ENIC Bureau (EB) and the NARIC Advisory Board (NAB) have drawn up a questionnaire addressed to the 55 member countries of the ENIC-NARIC network, which collects specific information on the measures adopted by each country for the award of final upper secondary school qualifications and for the holding and format of final exams. The responses received from the different countries are available on the enic-naric.net website¹¹.

In the school years 2019/2020 and 2020/2021, Ukrainian students were awarded the final secondary school qualification upon completion of the eleventh year, **without the obligation to take the final state exams (SFA)**. To limit the number of participants in the tests, **the opportunity of taking this exam was reserved only for students interested in continuing their university studies and therefore interested in taking a specific admission test - External Independent Evaluation - EIE**, the results of which are added to the final school leaving certificate in the lines for the SFA, and of course, the Certificate of the EIE and the Information Card are issued to participants.

In the documentation issued to students it is expressly indicated whether the student in question has taken the state exam SFA or not. In fact, in the *Addendum to the Certificate (Додаток до атестата/свідоцтва)*, and in particular, in the section dedicated to the results of the state exams taken, the expression “**звільнений**” (exempted) can be found for all those students who have not taken the state exam.

For more information, kindly consult the following document: Information on complete general secondary education qualification/level, and admission to higher education programs in Ukraine due to COVID-19¹².

¹¹ <https://www.enic-naric.net/upper-secondary-school-examinations-high-school-diplomas-in-times-of-covid-19.aspx>

¹² http://enic.in.ua/attachments/4all/%D0%A1%D0%90%D0%99%D0%A2_Info_school%20leaving%20certificate%20+%20EIE%20tests_ENG.pdf

2.3 Vocational (vocational-technical) education qualifications

As far as the qualifications of vocational (vocational-technical) education are concerned, it should be remembered that **until 1991 in Ukraine** such programmes were provided exclusively in the context of **secondary education** with a vocational focus, as in other national systems which make reference to the former Soviet Union system.

After the country's independence (1991) and after various reforms, some programmes became **part of the Ukrainian national system of short-term higher education** (Bologna Process short first-cycle qualifications/level 5 EQF), while others remained at the level of secondary school education. The denomination of these qualifications introduced since 1991 is the following:

Qualified Worker Diploma

Диплом кваліфікованого робітника

classified as part of the secondary school system

Junior Specialist Diploma (Junior Bachelor Diploma)

Диплом молодшого спеціаліста (Диплом молодшого бакалавра)

part of the higher education sector¹³

Access to the courses of Junior Specialist Diploma is allowed both on the basis of lower secondary school qualifications (Class 9) and upper secondary school (Class 11). Access to Junior Bachelor programs is allowed based on the basis of upper secondary education (Class 11) only.

2.4 Professional pre-higher education qualifications

Following the approval of the Law of Ukraine 'On Higher Education' in 2014, colleges and technical schools required new legal-normative foundation for organisation of their study process. Hence, in 2017, with the approval of the Law of Ukraine 'On Education' a new

¹³ For an in-depth analysis on the path necessary to be awarded this qualification, kindly refer to para 3.2.1 of Part 1 of this document.

component of the Ukrainian education system was introduced - professional pre-higher education - which was detailed in a separate law in 2019¹⁴.

Educational-professional programmes delivered at this level of education aim to equip their students with both solid theoretical and hands-on skills, for instance, via the dual mode of study.

The following qualification is awarded at the professional pre-higher education level which corresponds to level 5 NQF/EQF:

Diploma of Professional Junior Bachelor

Диплом фахового молодшого бакалавра

professional pre-higher education sector

Minimum access requirement for these study programmes includes lower secondary school qualifications (Class 9) and upper secondary school (Class 11), although holders of any other educational qualification of vocational (vocational-technical) education, professional pre-higher education or higher education are also eligible for enrollment. Professional Junior Bachelor degree has a workload from 120 - 180 to 240 ECTS, contingent upon completion of secondary education. Professional junior bachelor qualification gives access to continue education at the level of junior bachelor, bachelor and master of medical, pharmaceutical or veterinary specialization. The higher education institution may recognize and transfer the ECTS credits obtained at the professional junior bachelor's program, the maximum amount of which is determined by the relevant higher education standard.

List of specialties in the system of professional pre-higher education whose completion is required to access a regulated profession is approved by the respective Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine as of 2 September 2020 No 765¹⁵. The standards on professional pre-higher education specialties required for access to regulated professions¹⁶ may contain additional requirements for admission rules, educational program structure, learning scope, learning process and evaluation of graduates.

¹⁴ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2745-19#Text>

¹⁵ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/765-2020-%D0%BF#Text>

¹⁶ <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/osvita/fahova-peredvisha-osvita/sektor-fahovoyi-peredvishoyi-osviti/zatverdzeni-standarti>

3. HIGHER EDUCATION

In addition to having signed and ratified the Lisbon Convention (in 1997 and 2000, respectively), in 2005 Ukraine also joined the Bologna Process, thus becoming part of the European Higher Education Area - EHEA. As will be expanded upon later, this has brought about (and still implies) significant changes in the Ukrainian higher education system, promoting among other things ever increasing transparency of the qualifications of this system.

Source: <https://www.nuffic.nl/en/education-systems/ukraine/chart-education-system-in-ukraine>

3.1 Institutions and accreditation

The Ukrainian higher education system includes a total of around 600 of the following types of institutions:

- Universities – *університет*;
- Institutions – *інститут*;
- Academies – *академія*;
- Conservatories – *консерваторія* (now they are 'academies');
- Colleges – *коледж*.

3.1.1. Primary sources

A list of accredited higher education institutions is available:

- on the Ukrainian ENIC Centre website¹⁷ in Ukrainian, English and Russian;

- on the EDBO website¹⁸, available in Ukrainian and English. In particular, English-language information on Ukrainian HEIs can be downloaded as open data in the form of Excel from the EDEBO Register of educational institutions¹⁹. The same data are available for vocational (vocational-technical) and professional pre-higher education institutions.

¹⁷ <http://enic.in.ua/index.php/en/uipeng>

¹⁸ <https://registry.edbo.gov.ua/>

¹⁹ <https://registry.edbo.gov.ua/opendata/universities/>

Access to the two databases mentioned and whether they are functional are not guaranteed during this exceptional situation of conflict in which the country finds itself, therefore it is useful to remember the existence of an extremely important tool for such checks, namely the WayBackMachine system²⁰: this website database allows you to enter the address of any website and to trace the information available on this platform over the past years and months, a sort of “historical memorial” of websites.

3.1.2. Secondary sources (DEQAR e WHED)

The Database of External Quality Assurance Reports²¹ (in short: DEQAR) is a database of accreditation of higher education institutions and related study programmes recognised by quality assurance agencies at national level belonging to EQAR (European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education) and complying with ESG (European Standard and Guidelines) standards. Ukrainian normative base permits cross-border quality assurance of higher education²², therefore, different institutions and study programmes active in Ukraine can be searched in this database.

The IAU World Higher Education Database²³ (in short: IAU WHED) is a portal developed by the International Association of Universities in collaboration with UNESCO and, in addition to providing authoritative information on higher education systems in 196 countries and territories, contains a database of over 20,000 officially accredited and/or recognised higher education institutions, including those operating in Ukraine. It should be noted, however, that, unlike the other national sources and DEQAR, such information is entered directly by IAU with reference to its members, therefore the absence of an institution does not imply the certainty of non-accreditation of the same, but only an indication of the necessity to conduct further in-depth studies.

²⁰ <https://archive.org/web/>

²¹ <https://www.eqar.eu/qa-results/search/>

²² <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/554-2019-%D1%80#Text>

²³ <https://whed.net/home.php>

3.2 Elements of Higher Education Qualifications

3.2.1. Junior Specialist Diploma (Диплом молодшого спеціаліста)

Level	Bologna Process short first-cycle qualification/level 5 EQF
Duration	(a) from 1 to 3 years, if the access qualification is an upper secondary school qualification (Class 11); (b) from 2 to 4 years, if the access qualification is a lower secondary school qualification (Class 9).
Further details	The last admission to be awarded the aforementioned qualification was made in 2019. This qualification will therefore be gradually replaced by two new qualifications, the Junior Bachelor (<i>Молодший бакалавр</i>) and the Junior Professional Bachelor (<i>Фаховий молодший бакалавр</i>).
Access qualification	Lower secondary school qualification (Class 9) and Upper secondary school qualification (Class 11)

3.2.2. Diplom bakalavra (Диплом бакалавра)

Level	Bologna Process first-cycle qualification/level 6 EQF
Duration	4 years ²⁴
Access requirements	Upper secondary school final qualification (Class 11): <i>Атестат про повну загальну середню освіту/Свідоцтво про здобуття повної загальної середньої освіти</i>
Academic rights in Ukraine	Access to second-cycle study paths <i>Diplom magistra (Диплом магістра)</i> or <i>Diplom specialista (Диплом спеціаліста)</i> .
Other observations	First qualifications awarded as of 1993.

3.2.3. Diplom magistra (Диплом магістра)

Level	Bologna Process second-cycle qualification/level 7 EQF
Duration	1-2 years
Access requirements	<i>Diplom bakalavra (Диплом бакалавра)</i> or <i>Diplom specialista (Диплом спеціаліста)</i> .
Academic rights in Ukraine	Access to <i>Candidate of Science (Кандидат наук)/Doctor of Philosophy (Доктор філософії)/Doctor of Art (Доктор мистецтва)</i> study paths
Other observations	First qualifications awarded as of 1997. It is typically an academic path that includes the writing of a final thesis.

²⁴ Shorter durations are possible only if the access qualification is a *Junior Specialist Diploma (Диплом молодшого спеціаліста)* in related subjects, for which a course abbreviation may be granted.

3.2.4. *Dyplom specialista* (Диплом спеціаліста)

Level	Bologna Process second-cycle qualification/level 7 EQF
Duration	Varies according to the access qualifications, please see the following table.
Access requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upper secondary school final qualification (Class 11): <i>Атестат про повну загальну середню освіту/Свідоцтво про здобуття повної загальної середньої освіти</i> <i>Dyplom bakalavra</i> (Диплом бакалавра)
Academic rights in Ukraine	Access to <i>Dyplom magistra</i> (Диплом магістра) study paths or to <i>Candidate of Science</i> (Кандидат наук)/ <i>Doctor of Philosophy</i> (Доктор філософії)/ <i>Doctor of Art</i> (Доктор мистецтва)
Other observations	To obtain the final qualification, the passing of a State exam or, alternatively, the writing of a thesis may be required.

Access qualification and duration of study path:

Access qualification for <i>Dyplom specialista</i>	Duration of study path for <i>Dyplom specialista</i>
Upper secondary school final qualification (Class 11)	5-6 years (unique-cycle second-cycle qualification)
<i>Dyplom bakalavra</i> (Диплом бакалавра)	1-1.5 years (second-cycle qualification)

The examples below indicate the section of the **Academic Transcript - Додаток до диплома** which shows how the student concluded the course of ***Dyplom specialista* - Диплом спеціаліста**. In the first case there is a final thesis, while in the second case two state exams were taken without any final thesis.

Example 1 – Presence of a final thesis:

Thesis: "Economic and mathematical modeling of shadow processes in the economy of Lviv region"

Example 2 – State Exams with no final thesis:

ДОДАТКОВА ІНФОРМАЦІЯ

Тип закладу освіти: **вищий заклад освіти**
 IV рівня акредитації з правами автономії; форма власності – державна; підпорядкованість – Міністерство освіти і науки України
 Умови вступу: **за загальним конкурсом**

Вимоги програми навчання: **базова вища освіта з напрямку підготовки "Філологія"**

Навчальні заняття: **навчальний рік (два семестри) складається з 29 тижнів; навчальний тиждень - 54 години (26-27 годин аудиторних занять, 27-28 годин самостійної роботи)**

Система оцінюв: **поточні оцінки, семестрові заліки та екзамен, державні іспити і дипломна**

Додаток до диплома про вищу освіту № 34 (без диплома не дійсний)

Прізвище: _____
 Ім'я, по батькові: _____
 Дата народження: _____
 Попередній документ про освіту: **диплом бакалавра КВ № 30928006**
 Повна назва закладу освіти: **Київський національний лінгвістичний університет**
 Назва диплома: **диплом спеціаліста**
 Тип (вид) програми: **освітньо-професійна програма підготовки спеціаліста**
 Термін навчання: **10 місяців**
 Форма навчання: **денна**
 Напрямок підготовки (спеціальність): **"Переклад" (англійська та італійська мови)**
 Спеціалізація: _____
 Період практики: **перекладацька практика – 5 тижнів**

Атестація (державні іспити)	Оцінка
Теорія і практика перекладу англійської мови	добре
Теорія і практика перекладу італійської мови	відмінно

Рішенням державної екзаменаційної комісії від **06 червня 2008** р. присвоєно кваліфікацію: **філолог, перекладач англійської та італійської мов**

Attestation (State Examinations)

Name of the subject (course)	Grade
Theory and practice of English translation/interpretation	Good
Theory and practice of Italian translation/interpretation	Excellent

3.2.5. Candidate of Science (Кандидат наук) or Doctor of Philosophy (Доктор філософії)/Doctor of Art (Доктор мистецтва)

Level	Bologna Process third-cycle qualification/level 8 EQF
Duration	Minimum 3 years
Access requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diplom magistra (Диплом магістра) Diplom specialista (Диплом спеціаліста)
Academic rights in Ukraine	Access to <i>Doctor of Science (Доктор наук)</i> ²⁵
Other observations	The programme includes attending lectures/seminars and passing some exams, but the research element is predominant. The qualification is in fact issued by the specialised academic council and after the public defence of a thesis.

List of specialties in the system of higher education whose completion is required to access a regulated profession is approved by the respective MoES decree as of 22 May 2020 No 673²⁶. The standards on higher education specialties required

²⁵ The *Doctor of Science (Доктор наук)* is a research path following upon the *Candidate of Science (Кандидат наук)* qualification, at an extremely advanced level and higher than the third cycle qualifications of the Bologna Process. Although considered a final qualification that is part of the higher education system in Ukraine, in other countries this qualification may correspond to a research position subsequent to the Doctorate. The Doctor of Science scientific degree was excluded from the system of higher education after 31 March 2021.

²⁶ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1RV1dkzEskZJxy0A5iKC9HByd7ZIBfnyu>

for access to regulated professions²⁷ may contain additional requirements for admission rules, educational program structure, learning scope, learning process and evaluation of graduates²⁸.

4. Emergency measures adopted due to the war of the Russian Federation in Ukraine

The unprecedented brutal war aggression of the Russian Federation with support of Belarus in Ukraine called for ad hoc changes to the organisation of study process at all levels of education.

4.1 Admission into further studies and graduation

The legal framework for these changes is set in the Law of Ukraine 'On amendments to some laws of Ukraine in the field of education' as of 23 March, 2022 No 2157-IX²⁹ which details the following:

- 1 SFA was cancelled for all levels of secondary education for the graduates of 2021/2022, and in the educational documents in the line for the SFA results should be indicated "звільнено" (exempted);
- 2 Specific admission procedures for entrance into Junior Bachelor's, Bachelor's and Master's study programmes and professional pre-higher education institutions in 2022 are determined by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine.

The latter purported modifications³⁰ to the well-established assessment instruments of External Independent Evaluation, Unified Entrance Examination and Unified Professional Entrance Exam, and Unified State Qualification Exam for the year of 2022:

- External Independent Evaluation will be conducted in the form of the National Multi-subject Test (NMT) consisting of three subjects (Ukrainian language, Mathematics, History of Ukraine), in the format of proctored computer online testing in computer classrooms. As with EIE, NMT results will be required for enrolling into Bachelor study programmes;
- Traditional entrance exams for Master studies - Unified Entrance Examination

²⁷ <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/osvita/fahova-peredvisha-osvita/sektor-fahovoyi-peredvishoyi-osviti/zatverdzheni-standarti>

²⁸ <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/osvita/visha-osvita/naukovo-metodichna-rada-ministerstva-osviti-i-nauki-ukrayini/zatverdzheni-standarti-vishoyi-osviti>

²⁹ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2157-%D0%86%D0%A5#Text>

³⁰ <https://testportal.gov.ua/vstupni-vyprovuvannya-2022-roku/>

and Unified Professional Entrance Exam - have been suspended and re-defined in the form of Master's Comprehensive Test (MCT) and Master's Test of Educational Competence (MTEC). MCT will be carried out for applicants into study fields of Law (Право) and International Law (Міжнародне право), and will test their knowledge in foreign language and legal studies. Passing MTEC will be required for applicants into the following study fields: Social and behavioural studies (Соціальні та поведінкові науки), Journalism (Журналістика), Management and administration (Управління та адміністрування), Public management and administration (Публічне управління та адміністрування), and International Relations (Міжнародні відносини) (the latter - with the exception of the International Law). Both MCT and MTEC will be conducted in the format of proctored computer online testing. Access to Master studies for applicants into other study fields will be based on exams carried out by educational institutions, or a motivation letter³¹;

- Unified State Qualification Exam for graduates from selected study fields has been cancelled³² and professional pre-higher and higher education institutions are responsible for defining the form of final attestation and its delivery in accordance with their individual situation.

Applicants to Bachelor and Master studies will sit NMT, MCT or MTEC during certain periods in summer 2022 which are defined based on the security situation in Ukraine³³.

At present, MoES works on ensuring access to these assessment instruments by persons who wish to enrol into Ukrainian colleges and universities both in Ukraine, and from abroad³⁴: support by the EU hosting countries is sought after with regard to forming a distributed network of testing points, e.g., at the premises of foreign HEIs, and finding proctors and supervisors for these exams.

Admission into professional pre-higher studies will be administered by their respective educational institutions that are enabled to use the instruments of art competition, individual interview and motivation letter³⁵.

³¹ https://mon.gov.ua/storage/app/media/news/2022/04/01/Vstupna.Kampaniya.2022-01.04.pdf?fbclid=IwAR3Kn_uaUCEPRakclm9DEPthybMKg3NvNeqXUtB9i26Ew1gtRvfDNmLhLYE

³² <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/376-2022-%D0%BF#n2>

³³ http://search.ligazakon.ua/l_doc2.nsf/link1/RE37823.html

³⁴ <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/news/nmt-mozhna-sklasti-yak-v-ukrayini-tak-i-za-kordonom-ale-fizichna-prisutnist-obov'yazkova-ministr-osviti-i-nauki>

³⁵ http://search.ligazakon.ua/l_doc2.nsf/link1/RE37822.html

4.2 Educational documents

Since 24 February 2022, more than 7,7 million³⁶ Ukrainians have become internally displaced and another 5,5 million³⁷ had to leave the country. In view of this, MoES regularly provides ad hoc guidelines on measures to be taken as regards possible loss and/or absence of educational documents for people who had to evacuate to safer regions. At present, MoES contributes its efforts to several initiatives on digitalization and digital transformation of educational documents and works towards ensuring their easy and safe usage by Ukrainian qualification holders. Until then, the up-to-date guidelines for different levels of education are as follows.

School qualifications

The qualification holder, or his/her legally authorised representative, has to contact the institution that issued the educational documents. Persons who have completed general secondary education in educational institutions in the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine, including temporarily occupied territories in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions, may contact any complete general secondary education institution at their current place of residence³⁸.

In the absence of a certificate on the results of the annual evaluation of academic achievements, the institution evaluates the knowledge of the graduate in accordance with the Procedure for accounting and issuance of documents on general secondary education of the state standard to persons who completed general secondary education in educational institutions on the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine, as approved by the MoES decree as of 12 May 2014 No 570³⁹.

To obtain a duplicate of the school qualification, its holder may request any complete general secondary education institution, on whose territory no military operations take place at the time of such request, to provide information about such a document issued in Ukraine.

³⁶ IOM, data as of 17 April 2022, <https://displacement.iom.int/reports/ukraine-internal-displacement-report-general-population-survey-round-3-11-17-april-2022>

³⁷ UNHCR, data as of 1 May 2022, <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/situations/ukraine>

³⁸ https://mon.gov.ua/ua/news/procedura-otrimannya-dublikata-dokumenta-pro-zagalnu-serednyu-osvitu?fbclid=IwARONi_fodnXJOPIMXLDTbuepZZ9UdNf761rbOF5GUSQpF2xqB7SIXbiFzVI

³⁹ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0541-14#Text>

Vocational (vocational-technical) qualifications

The qualification holder can have his/her educational document re-issued following the respective request to the institution that issued the educational documents.

If the vocational (vocational-technical) education institution has ceased its activities, a person can forward the request to its successor, the information on which is provided by the Department of Education and Science of the regional military administration. In the absence of a successor institution, the request has to be submitted to the Department of Education and Science of the regional military administration, which determines the institution that will order and issue a duplicate of the educational document⁴⁰.

Professional pre-higher and higher education qualifications

In case of loss of the higher education document, the educational institution is responsible for producing its duplicate, in line with the Procedure on ordering, production, issuance, accounting of documents on higher education and appendices to diplomas of European standard, as approved by the MoES decree as of 6 March 2015 No 249⁴¹.

Duplicates of higher education documents and their annexes are prepared and issued upon a written application of the qualification holder, submitted by him/her or a legally authorised representative, to the educational institution that issued the higher education document.

If the educational institution that issued the document is reorganised through merger, amalgamation or liquidation, the request is submitted to its successor.

In the absence of a successor of the terminated educational institution, and in case the educational institution does not conduct educational activities (e. g., for reasons of a revoked licence to carry out educational activities, or location of the educational institution on the territory outside the control of the Ukrainian authorities), the request is submitted to MoES. In this situation, MoES determines the educational institution that creates in the Unified State Electronic Database on Education (EDEBO) orders, prepares and issues a higher education document or its duplicate⁴².

⁴⁰ <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/ministerstvo/pro-ministerstvo/najposhirenishi-zapitannya-vidpovidi-ta-aktualni-kontakti-mon-pid-chas-voyennogo-stanu/najposhirenishi-zapitannya-vidpovidi/profesijna-profesijno-tehnichnoyi-osvita>

⁴¹ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0494-15#n4>

⁴² <https://mon.gov.ua/ua/ministerstvo/pro-ministerstvo/najposhirenishi-zapitannya-vidpovidi-ta-aktualni-kontakti-mon-pid-chas-voyennogo-stanu/najposhirenishi-zapitannya-vidpovidi/fahova-peredvisha-visha-osvita>

PART 2: ANALYSIS OF ACADEMIC QUALIFICATIONS AND RELATIVE DOCUMENTATION

1. GENERAL OBSERVATIONS

To deepen the documentary aspect of the qualifications described above, it is necessary to keep in mind that over the years in Ukraine there have been a number of slightly different final qualification formats. An extremely useful database can be found on the website of the Ukrainian ENIC *National Information Centre of Academic Mobility*⁴³, inasmuch as it is complete and edited directly by the national centre itself.

Under the section “*Samples of educational documents*”, it is possible to choose between the following categories of qualifications:

- a secondary education;
- b vocational education;
- c postgraduate education;
- d higher education.

Within the selected category, there are the names of the individual qualifications with a detailed explanation of the main characteristics that each diploma presents according to the year of issue of the qualification: colour, size, materials (paper or plastic), signatures, stamps and serial numbers.

The screenshot displays the ENIC Ukraine National Information Centre of Academic Mobility website. The header includes the logo (four colored circles: green, yellow, orange, red) and the text 'ENIC UKRAINE National Information Centre of Academic Mobility INFORMATION AND IMAGE CENTER STATE-OWNED COMPANY MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE OF UKRAINE'. Language options 'EN RU UA' are visible in the top right. A navigation bar contains 'Main', 'News', 'Useful Links', and 'Digests'. The main content area is divided into a left sidebar and a main text area. The sidebar lists: 'ENIC-NARIC Network', 'Education system of Ukraine', 'Samples of educational documents' (highlighted with a red box), 'Regulatory Framework', 'List of Ukrainian HEIs', 'Verification of apostilles issued by MES', 'Education systems of the world', and 'Services and Contact Information'. The main text area is titled 'Samples of educational documents' and 'EDUCATIONAL DOCUMENTS IN UKRAINE'. It contains a paragraph explaining that samples are systematized by year from 1961 to the present, noting a transition period where old and new designs were used. A second paragraph states that due to the 'Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education"' dated September 6, 2014, rules for higher education documents changed. A third paragraph notes that a unified sample of higher education documents does not exist, but some requirements for layout and registration at the 'Higher Education Document Register' (USEDE) are mandatory. The text concludes with: 'Therefore we can distinguish such stages of change in the educational document layout:'.

⁴³ <http://enic.in.ua/index.php/en/educational-documents-samples>

1.1 Usage and relevance of national format (*State-standard Diplomas*)

All Ukrainian secondary school qualifications as well as higher education qualifications issued until 2015 are presented in a national format (the so-called *State-standard*). This means that the qualifications are issued according to a design established at national level and valid for all scholastic, vocational and higher education institutions. Another element to take into consideration relates to the fact that only official institutions - recognised and/or accredited by the competent Ukrainian authorities - are authorised to issue their qualifications in the national format.

This “standard” design is uniform both from the graphic point of view and as regards the information reported therein.

From the point of view of the production process, the printing of these qualifications is commissioned directly by the Ministry of Education and Sciences (*Міністерство освіти і науки*), which subsequently distributes the documents (pre-filled in their general parts and already equipped with the so-called security features i.e., document anti-counterfeiting systems) to the institutions that will later release them. The latter, on the other hand, are responsible for filling in the specific fields referring to the individual qualification (surname, name and patronymic of the student, date of issue and marks obtained).

This approach has direct implications in the evaluation of qualifications, in particular with regard to the following aspects:

Authenticity of the qualification: knowledge of the graphic format and of the information provided in a qualification issued within a given time frame facilitates the comparison of the qualification being assessed with the national design of reference. In the event of significant differences, a verification of the authenticity of the qualification will become necessary.

Accreditation of the awarding institution: once it has been ascertained that a certain qualification is presented in State-standard format and after having verified its authenticity, it can be assumed that the institution that issued it is accredited,

as authorisation to issue qualifications in the State-standard format is contingent upon accreditation of the awarding institution, specialty, and/or study programme.

Given this peculiarity of the Ukrainian system, it is advisable to have an internal database of qualifications already evaluated and referring to the given education system, so as to be able to compare the new qualifications received directly with those already evaluated.

Finally, please note that the State-standard format has been modified over the years and that it is available for all scholastic qualifications issued to date and for university qualifications until 2015.

1.2 Periodisation of formats

Since the formats established at national level have varied slightly over the years, a general periodisation is provided below, which will be analysed more in depth when examining the individual qualifications dealt with:

Paper qualifications were issued from 1992 to 2000, which were subsequently filled in by hand by the awarding Institutions. These qualifications can be found in bilingual form (Ukrainian-Russian) or in monolingual form (Ukrainian).

Since 1997, the new plastic card-type qualifications have been released, which have different formats and are currently only issued for secondary school qualifications.

Since 2015, higher education institutions have replaced the aforementioned plastic card-type qualifications with internal formats, while respecting certain characteristics established at the national level by law.

1.3 Guide to the interpretation of qualifications in plastic card format

The details of the most common State-standard formats of laminated cards in plastic card format follow.

- 1 **The front of the qualification** shows only the name of the qualification (in this case it is the final upper secondary school qualification awarded until 2018/ *Атестат про повну загальну середню освіту*).

- 2 **The back of the qualification** on the other hand shows the following details:
 - Surname, name and patronymic of the student (black box)
 - Year of qualification (red box)
 - Awarding institution (blue underline)
 - Award date of qualification (yellow box)
 - Series and serial number: alphanumeric code that uniquely identifies the qualification (green box)

2. LOWER AND UPPER SECONDARY SCHOOL QUALIFICATIONS

Before specifically analysing upper secondary school qualifications, it is first of all necessary to mention two possible methods to distinguish the latter from lower secondary school qualifications: from a terminological point of view, despite having assumed different names over the years, there are some key words to pay particular attention to in order to distinguish between final lower secondary school qualifications (i.e., 9 years of overall schooling) and final upper secondary school qualifications (11 years of overall schooling):

- 1 In the case of **lower secondary school qualifications**, there are some terms that can help identify them. We are talking specifically about the adjectives **неповний – incomplete** and **базовий – basic**:

- Свідоцтво про **неповну** загальну середню освіту - Certificate of **Incomplete** General Secondary Education
- Свідоцтво про **базову** загальну середню освіту - Certificate of **Basic** General Secondary Education
- Свідоцтво про здобуття **базової** середньої освіти - Certificate of **Basic** Secondary Education (name used as of 2019)

- 2 The same method can be applied in the case of **upper secondary school qualifications**. It is a question of identifying the adjective **повний – complete** within the name of the qualification:

- Аттестат про **повну** загальну середню освіту - Certificate of **Complete** General Secondary Education
- Свідоцтво про здобуття **повної** загальної середньої освіти - Certificate of **Complete** General Secondary Education (name used as of 2019)

Even the graphic elements present in the final qualifications ensure the possibility of easily identifying them, in fact:

- a Lower secondary school qualifications are presented in a green frame (figure 1)
- b Upper secondary school qualifications are presented in a grey-blue frame (figure 2)

Figure 1: Lower secondary school qualification (Class 9)

Figure 2: Higher secondary school qualification (Class 11)

2.1 Upper secondary school qualifications

The upper secondary school qualifications were issued in paper format from 1992 to 2000, while as early as 1997, the first laminated plastic card-type qualifications began to be issued. In addition to this it is also important to remember that:

- 1 Since 2019, the name of the qualification has changed from *Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education* (Атестат про повну загальну середню освіту) to *Certificate of Complete General Secondary Education* (Свідоцтво про здобуття повної загальної середньої освіти).
- 2 Secondary school qualifications (including upper secondary school qualifications) are still issued in the *State-standard* format.

Below are the main formats of upper secondary school qualifications (10 years of schooling until 1994 and 11 years of schooling starting from 1995):

Reference period: 1992-2000 (monolingual version)

Reference period: 1997-2012

Front

Back

Reference period: 2013-2018

Front

Back

Reference period: from 2019

Front

Back

All upper secondary school qualifications are accompanied by a document called **Додаток до Атестації / Свідоцтва - Academic Transcript**:

Guidelines on fast-track recognition of Ukrainian Academic Qualifications

As regards the **grading system**, it is important to remember that the knowledge of pupils is measured on a 12-point scale with marks ranging from 1 to 12. Maximum grade is 12, minimum grade is 1, below 1 is “unattested” mark, and marks’ general classification is as follows:

- Level I. Elementary (1-3)
- Level II. Average (4-6)
- Level III. Sufficient (7-9)
- Level IV. High (10-12)

The **Додаток до Атестації / Свідоцтва - Academic Transcript** contains information on the courses attended (red box), the marks obtained (yellow box) and the subjects in which the final exam was taken, with the respective marks (green box).

ДОДАТОК ДО АТЕСТАЦІЇ
про повну загальну середню освіту
№ 45304135
(без атестата не дійсний)

██████████
(прізвище, ім'я, по батькові)

закінчила у 20 13 році
комунальний заклад "Луганська вечірня
(повна назва навчального закладу)
(змінна) школа II-III ступенів"

з такими балами:

назва предмета	бал
Українська мова	п'ять
Українська література	дев'ять
Російська мова	п'ять
Література	дев'ять
Художня культура	шість
Інформатика	вісім
Алгебра і початки аналізу	шість
Геометрія	чотири
Історія України	шість
Всесвітня історія	п'ять
Правознавство	вісім
Фізика	шість

Астрономія	чотири
Хімія	сім
Біологія	вісім
Географія	сім
Основи економіки	сім
Іноземна мова (англ.)	десять
Екологія	шість

Пройшла державну підсумкову атестацію з таких предметів:

назва предмета	бал
Українська мова	сім
Українська література	десять
Історія України	дев'ять
Середній бал атестата	6,9 - 151,6 б.

3. TVET QUALIFICATIONS: *Junior Specialist Diploma (Диплом молодшого спеціаліста)* and *Qualified Worker Diploma (Диплом кваліфікованого робітника)*

For both the qualifications of *Junior Specialist Diploma - Диплом молодшого спеціаліста* and the *Qualified Worker Diploma - Диплом кваліфікованого робітника*, the final diplomas were issued in paper format until 2000, while the first laminated plastic card-type format qualifications were being released as of 1997.

It is worth noting that as of 2015, *Junior Specialist Diploma - Диплом молодшого спеціаліста* qualifications have been issued in formats established independently by higher education institutions, while *Qualified Worker Diploma - Диплом кваліфікованого робітника* qualifications continue to be issued in the State-standard format, like all secondary school qualifications. This distinction is due to the current Ukrainian law, which states that:

- the *Qualified Worker Diploma - Диплом кваліфікованого робітника* is not considered to be part of the higher education system;
- the *Junior Specialist Diploma - Диплом молодшого спеціаліста* is considered part of the higher education system and identified as a Bologna Process short first-cycle qualification, that is, level 5 EQF.

Reference period: 1992-2000 (monolingual version)

Reference period: 1993-2000 - Qualified Worker Diploma

Reference period: from 1997 until today - Qualified Worker Diploma in various formats

Reference period: from 1997 to 2015 - Junior Specialist Diploma in various formats

Reference period: from 2015 until 2021 - Junior Specialist Diploma (example of a format referring to a single institution)⁴⁴

⁴⁴ The example shown therefore has an illustrative value, being the specific format of a single institution (in this case it is the Київський національний торговельно-економічний університет /Kyiv National University of Trade and Economics).

4. BOLOGNA PROCESS FIRST- AND SECOND-CYCLE QUALIFICATIONS

The main academic qualifications of the Ukrainian higher education system are as follows:

- a *Dyplom bakalavra* - *Диплом бакалавра*
- b *Dyplom magistra* - *Диплом магістра*
- c *Dyplom specialista* - *Диплом спеціаліста*

For all these qualifications we find some common characteristics from a chronological point of view applied to the documentation released, namely:

- 1 1992-2000: paper qualifications in standard format compiled by hand by the higher education institutions in the parts relating to the details of the individual diploma. This format is not found in the qualifications of *Dyplom magistra* (*Диплом магістра*) as this title was not issued before 1997;
- 2 1997-2015: laminated qualifications in plastic card-type format;
- 3 From 2015 until today: qualifications awarded according to formats established independently by the universities, mainly bilingual (Ukrainian-English) following the mandatory state requirements.

a. *Dyplom bakalavra* - *Диплом бакалавра*

Reference period: 1993-2000 - Qualified Worker Diploma

Reference period: from 1997 to 2015 - Junior Specialist Diploma in various formats

Reference period: from 2015 until 2021 (examples of formats referring to two different institutions)⁴⁵

⁴⁵ The examples shown are therefore illustrative, as the formats are specific to two individual institutions.

Front

Back

b. *Diplom magistra* - Диплом магістра

Reference period: 1997-2015 (in various formats)

Reference period: from 2015 until 2021 (examples of formats referring to two different institutions)⁴⁶

⁴⁶ The examples shown are therefore illustrative, as the formats are specific to two individual institutions.

с. *Diplom specialista* - Диплом спеціаліста

Reference period: 1993-2000

Reference period: 1997-2015 (in various formats)

*Reference period: from 2015 until today
(example of format referring to a single institution)⁴⁷*

⁴⁷ The example shown is therefore illustrative, as the format is specific to one individual institution.

The following image on the other hand reproduces the second page of the document with details relating to the main elements of the qualification, inserted in the third column:

<http://enic.in.ua/>

4.2. Diploma Supplement

As of 2015, another document of great use in evaluating higher education qualifications was introduced in Ukraine: the Diploma Supplement. The latter, conforming to the standard developed within the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), contains relevant information such as, among others, the name and status of the awarding institution and, if the institution is different, information on the teaching institution, as well as the workload expressed in ECTS credits.

3.1 Детальний опис програми (англійською, українською або російською мовами). English detailed description of the program.

Номер за програмою або код Course code	Назва Дисципліни/Course title	Навчальний рік/Study year	Кредити/ECTS (всього/ECTS credits (total))	Бали/Mark	Оцінка за національним/міжнародним рівнем/ National grade	Рівень ЄКВТ/ECTS grade
1	Біологія / Biology	2006/2007	7 (210)	76	Добре / Good	D
2	Зоологія / Zoology	2006/2007	7 (210)	81	Добре / Good	C
3	Загальна біологія / General biology	2006/2007	4,5 (135)	89	Добре / Good	B
4	Математика / Mathematics	2006/2007	9 (180)	92	Відмінно / Excellent	A
5	Українська мова / Ukrainian language for professional direction	2006/2007	2 (60)	76	Добре / Good	B
6	Українська мова (професійна)	2006/2007	1,5 (45)	76	Задовільно / Passed	D
7	Анатомія рослин / Plant Anatomy	2006/2007	1,5 (45)	92	Відмінно / Excellent	B
8	Гістологія / Histology	2006/2007	1,5 (45)	99	Відмінно / Excellent	B
9	Фізика (1-3 семестри) / Physics (1-3 semesters)	2007/2008	10,5 (315)	94	Відмінно / Excellent	A
10	Українська мова (англійська, 1-4 семестри) / Foreign Language (English, 1-4 semesters)	2007/2008	8,5 (255)	73	Задовільно / Passed	D
11	Хімія (неорганічна, аналітична та фізична, органічна, біоорганічна) / Chemistry (Inorganic, Analytical and Physical Organic, Bioorganic) (1-4 Semesters)	2007/2008	27 (810)	72	Задовільно / Passed	C
12	Термодинаміка / Thermodynamics	2007/2008	3 (90)	80	Задовільно / Passed	C
13	Інформатика / Informatics	2007/2008	3 (90)	92	Відмінно / Excellent	B
14	Фізика (4 семестри) / Physics (4 semesters)	2007/2008	5,5 (165)	84	Добре / Good	C
15	Вступ до спеціальності біологія / Introduction to the specialty of biology	2007/2008	1,5 (45)	90	Відмінно / Excellent	B
16	Біологія / Biology	2007/2008	1,5 (45)	83	Задовільно / Passed	C
17	Біологія (вступ до спеціальності) / Biology (individual development)	2007/2008	1,5 (45)	82	Добре / Good	C
18	Анатомія людини / Human Anatomy	2007/2008	1 (90)	70	Задовільно / Passed	E
19	Мікробіологія / Microbiology	2007/2008	1 (120)	89	Добре / Good	B
20	Соціологія / Sociology	2007/2008	1 (60)	85	Задовільно / Passed	C
21	Безпека життєвості / Safety	2007/2008	1,5 (45)	90	Відмінно / Excellent	B
22	Фізіологія людини та тварин / Physiology and Biochemistry	2008/2009	6,5 (195)	81	Добре / Good	C
23	Фізіологія людини та тварин / Physiology of human and animal	2008/2009	6,5 (195)	78	Добре / Good	C
24	Міжлекарська біологія / Molecular Biology	2008/2009	3 (120)	88	Добре / Good	B
25	Фізіологія / Physiology	2008/2009	4 (120)	87	Добре / Good	A
26	Біологія / Biology	2008/2009	4 (120)	98	Відмінно / Excellent	A
27	Теорія еволюції / Theory of evolution	2008/2009	3 (90)	88	Задовільно / Passed	B
28	Математичні методи в біології / Mathematical methods in biology	2008/2009	3 (90)	94	Задовільно / Passed	A
Всього кредитів ЄКВТ / Total credits ECTS			240 (7200)			
Загальна оцінка / Total mark and rank				85	Добре / Good	B

5. THIRD-CYCLE QUALIFICATIONS

In this section we highlight an example of a third cycle degree: it is a **Doctor of Philosophy - Доктор філософії/Doctor of Art - Доктор мистецтва** qualifications. It is important to remember that all third-cycle qualifications are issued by the **Supreme Attestation Commission of Ukraine - Вища атестаційна комісія України/Specialised academic council of higher education institution or research institution**, therefore this nomenclature is specified within the final qualification:

6. REVISIONS OF EDUCATIONAL DOCUMENTS' FORMATS IN 2021

In 2021, MoES introduced changes⁴⁸ to the forms of diplomas of Junior Bachelor, Bachelor, Master, Doctor of Philosophy, Doctor of Fine Arts, Doctor of Sciences⁴⁹, as well as to the form of their Diploma Supplement.

Following these revisions, the Diploma Supplement issued by Ukrainian higher educational institutions fully corresponds to the revised Diploma Supplement, as approved by the Paris Communiqué of the European Higher Education Area. It also contains detailed information on the national higher education system, such as on types of higher education institutions and their status, educational programmes and degrees, licensing and accreditation processes, organization, structure of higher education studies, and official sources of information.

The up-to-date forms of these qualifications are presented below:

Reference period: from 2021 until today - Junior Specialist Diploma⁵⁰

⁴⁸ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0122-21#Text>

⁴⁹ At the time of writing this publication, changes are being introduced to the form of Doctor of Sciences diploma, with the aim to re-new its form approved by the MoES decree as of 12 May, 2015 No 525 (<https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0551-15#Text>).

⁵⁰ Students who have enrolled into a Junior Specialist educational programme until 2019 inclusive obtain a Diploma of Junior Specialist that is equated to the Diploma of Junior Bachelor upon successful completion of studies.

Reference period: from 2021 until today – Bachelor Diploma

Reference period: from 2021 until today – Master Diploma

Reference period: from 2021 until today – Doctor of Philosophy Diploma

Front

Back

Reference period: from 2021 until today – Diploma Supplement

Part 2: Analysis of academic qualifications and relative documentation

Код освітньої записки (написки)	Назва освітньої записки або результату навчання / Скорочена назва або learning outcome	Кількість кредитів / Європейський еквівалент / трансферне кредитів / Number of ECTS credits	Оцінка за запискою / Інституційний клас / Institutional Grade
1	Історія України / History of Ukraine	60	Дуже / Good
2	Історія української культури / History of Ukrainian Culture	4	Дуже / Good
3	Углублена мова (або професійне спілкування) / Advanced Language (or Professional Proficiency)	5	Відмінно / Excellent
4	Філософія (філософські теми, есеї, курси) / Philosophy (Philosophical Topics, Essays, Courses)	6	Відмінно / Excellent
5	Математика / Mathematics	4	Відмінно / Excellent
6	Основи безпеки життєдіяльності та здоров'я / Fundamentals of Life Safety and Health Protection	4	Відмінно / Excellent
7	Основи медицини / Fundamentals of Medicine	4	Відмінно / Excellent
8	Висока фізична підготовка та здоров'я / High Physical and Health Preparation	3	Зарядково / Passed
9	Основи інформаційних систем та ТІТ / Fundamentals of Information Systems and IT	3	Зарядково / Passed
10	Математика та статистика / Mathematics and Statistics	3	Зарядково / Passed
11	Правознавство / Law	3	Зарядково / Passed

Код освітньої записки (написки)	Назва освітньої записки або результату навчання / Скорочена назва або learning outcome	Кількість кредитів / Європейський еквівалент / трансферне кредитів / Number of ECTS credits	Оцінка за запискою / Інституційний клас / Institutional Grade
12	Вступ до міжнародних та культурно-історичних студій / Introduction to Cultural, Linguistics and History of Contemporary Studies	3,5	Дуже / Good
13	Спеціальні курси / Special Courses	4	90
14	Вступ до психології / Introduction to Psychology	5	Зарядково / Passed
15	Психологія / Psychology	5	Відмінно / Excellent
16	Психологія / Psychology	5	Відмінно / Excellent
17	Методи викладання англійської мови / Teaching Methods of English Language	3,5	Відмінно / Excellent
18	Вступ до англійської мови / Introduction to English Language	3,5	Дуже / Good
19	Практична англійська мова / Practical English Language	6	Відмінно / Excellent
20	Практична англійська мова / Practical English Language	3,5	Відмінно / Excellent
21	Практична англійська мова / Practical English Language	3,5	Відмінно / Excellent
22	Лексика та граматика / Lexicology and Grammar	3	Відмінно / Excellent
23	Історія мови та мови / History of English Language	3	Відмінно / Excellent
24	Практична англійська мова / Practical English Language	19,5	Удовільно / Passed
25	Практична англійська мова / Practical English Language	3	Відмінно / Excellent
26	Курсова робота з курсу англійської мови / Coursework in English Language	1	Відмінно / Excellent
27	Курсова робота з курсу англійської мови / Coursework in English Language	1	90
28	Курсова робота з курсу англійської мови / Coursework in English Language	3	91
29	Курсова робота з курсу англійської мови / Coursework in English Language	6	Зарядково / Passed
30	Курсова робота з курсу англійської мови / Coursework in English Language	3,5	Відмінно / Excellent
31	Курсова робота з курсу англійської мови / Coursework in English Language	3,5	Зарядково / Passed

Код освітньої записки (написки)	Назва освітньої записки або результату навчання / Скорочена назва або learning outcome	Кількість кредитів / Європейський еквівалент / трансферне кредитів / Number of ECTS credits	Оцінка за запискою / Інституційний клас / Institutional Grade
1	2	3	4
32	Українська мова та історична графіка / Ukrainian Language and Historical Graphics	25	Відмінно / Excellent
33	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	10	Відмінно / Excellent
34	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	90
35	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	1	Відмінно / Excellent
36	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	1	Відмінно / Excellent
37	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	Відмінно / Excellent
38	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	Відмінно / Excellent
39	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	Відмінно / Excellent
40	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	Відмінно / Excellent
41	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	2	90
42	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	95
43	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	Відмінно / Excellent
44	Українська філософія та історична графіка / Ukrainian Philosophy and Historical Graphics	3	Відмінно / Excellent

4.4 Система оцінювання та, за наявності, таблиця розподілу оцінок	4.4 Grading system and, if available, grade distribution table
За шкалою від 100 балів / On the 100-point scale	За національною шкалою / On a national scale
90-100 балів / points	Відмінно / Excellent
80-89 балів / points	Дуже / Good
70-79 балів / points	Задовільно / Satisfactory
60-69 балів / points	Незадовільно / Fail
0-59 балів / points	Неприйнятно / Unsatisfactory
Мінімальний проходний бал / Minimum pass mark - 60	

6. ДОДАТКОВА ІНФОРМАЦІЯ	6. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION
6.1 Інформація про освітню записку / Additional information on the certificate	6.1 Additional information
6.1.1 Найменування висхідної записки / Name of the higher education institution	6.1.2 Строк навчання в семестрі / Duration of training in each of them
6.2 Інша інформація / Other information	6.2 Further information sources
84116, Україна, Донецька обл., м. Слов'янськ, вул. Ватська, 19, тел.: +38(0)62 66-54-54 E-mail: ap@slav.dn.ua	84116, Ukraine, Donetsk region, Sloviansk, 19, Vatskaya Str. tel.: +38(0)6262 66-54-54 http://www.dfnpu.edu.ua E-mail: ap@slav.dn.ua

7. ЗАСВІДЧЕННЯ ДОДАТКА ДО ДИПЛОМА	7. CERTIFICATION OF THE SUPPLEMENT TO THE DIPLOMA
7.1 Дата / 7.1 Date	7.1 Date
01/07/2021	01/07/2021
7.2 Підпис / 7.2 Signature	7.2 Signature
7.3 Керівник або уповноважена особа / 7.3 Chief or authorized person	7.3 Chief or authorized person
7.4 Підпис / 7.4 Initials and stamp or seal	7.4 Initials, Print Name, Last Name

Other important changes to issuing of documents on higher education in Ukraine include:

- 1 Documents on higher education can be issued by higher education institutions **only for accredited educational programmes (programme subject areas)**. Information on accreditation decisions is included into EDEBO, and can be reviewed in the section 'Educational programmes' (*Освітні програми*) on the individual institutional webpage in the EDEBO register of state-recognized education institutions⁵¹, or in the register of accreditation cases⁵² administered by the Ukraine's National Agency for Higher Education Quality Assurance;
- 2 Starting 1 January 2022, diplomas of Doctor of Philosophy and Doctor of Fine Arts, as well as the Diploma Supplement are registered and **assigned a registration number in EDEBO**. Therefore, the information on these documents issued since that date becomes available in EDEBO for verification purposes;

Separate forms of education documents 'with honours' (*з відзнакою*) have

- 3 been cancelled, and currently information on **special academic achievements** of a qualification holder may be indicated in the section '6.1 Additional information' of the Diploma Supplement. The decision to reflect these achievements lies within the responsibility of the awarding higher education institution;
- 4 As per updated to the Law of Ukraine 'On Higher Education' from December 2019, **the concept of the state-standard format of higher education documents has been revoked**, and the emphasis lies with the list of mandatory information to be present in documents on higher education (scientific degrees)⁵³ and on professional pre-higher education⁵⁴. For instance, academic councils of higher education institutions may approve the forms and procedures for issuing higher education documents, including joint and double diplomas.

⁵¹ <https://registry.edbo.gov.ua/>

⁵² <https://public.naqa.gov.ua/>

⁵³ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/811-2020-%D0%BF#Text>

⁵⁴ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0787-21#Text>

MoES also approved in 2021 the **forms of the diploma of Professional Junior Bachelor and the form of its Diploma Supplement**⁵⁵, the latter following the model of the Diploma Supplement for higher education qualifications.

Enrollments into Professional Junior Bachelor have commenced since 2020. The first graduation of those admitted to studies on the basis on complete general secondary education will take place in 2022.

In 2021, its first qualification holders, who had been admitted to studies on the basis of Qualified Worker Diploma (*Диплом кваліфікованого робітника*), were awarded the diplomas of Professional Junior Bachelor.

The up-to-date forms of these qualifications are presented below:

Reference period: from 2021 until today – Doctor of Philosophy Diploma

⁵⁵ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z0786-21#Text>

PART 3: VERIFICATION RESOURCES TO DETERMINE AUTHENTICITY

1. UNIFIED STATE ELECTRONIC DATABASE ON EDUCATION

To allow easier and more reliable verification of the authenticity of qualifications issued in Ukraine, the Ministry of Education and Sciences has created a platform called ***Unified State Electronic Database on Education -Єдина державна електронна база з питань освіти***⁵⁶, in the abbreviated form ***EDEBO/ЄДЕБО***.

EDEBO is the central Higher Education Management Information System in Ukraine deployed for evidence-based policymaking on formation, implementation, and monitoring of higher education policies. This system collects information on students' applications, enrollment, and graduation, and is the focal point for the annual competitive enrollment campaign into vocational (vocational-technical) and higher education institutions. EDEBO consists of several registers, namely the register of state-recognized education institutions, the register of educational documents, the register of student cards, and the register of teachers' certificates. EDEBO plays a key role in all digital transformation projects⁵⁷ in the higher education sector that the Ukrainian Government works on, including the graduate tracking system, distance enrollment of foreign students into Ukrainian universities, and e-licensing of educational institutions.

1.1. Verification of educational documents

Via EDEBO it is possible to verify the authenticity of qualifications⁵⁸ issued in the plastic card format for the following categories:

- Lower secondary school
- Upper secondary school
- Vocational education
- Higher education, including qualifications issued since 2015 in the formats established autonomously by the individual institutions

⁵⁶ The resource can be consulted only in Ukrainian at the following link: <https://info.edbo.gov.ua/edu-documents/>

⁵⁷ <https://plan2.diiia.gov.ua/projects>

⁵⁸ <https://info.edbo.gov.ua/edu-documents/>

Once the link to the register of educational documents has opened, the following screen will appear:

In order to verify the authenticity of a qualification, it will be necessary to select:

- **in the first drop-down menu** the category to which the qualification in question belongs (higher education, vocational training or secondary school);
- **in the second drop-down menu** the name of the qualification.

Guidelines on fast-track recognition of Ukrainian Academic Qualifications

In the following fields, on the other hand, you will be asked to enter the following fields (in Ukrainian, therefore exclusively in Cyrillic characters):

- The series (**red** box).
- The serial number (**yellow** box).
- Surname, name and patronymic (**green** box)

РЕЕСТР ДОКУМЕНТІВ ПРО ОСВІТУ

ДАНИ ДОКУМЕНТА ПРО ОСВІТУ

Документи про вищу освіту

Оберть тип документа

Серія *

Номер *

ДАНИ ОСОБИ

Прізвище *

Ім'я *

По батькові

Підтверджую, по батькові відсутнє

PEC

Введіть символи, що зображені вище

Надіслати запит

SUBMIT

Series (e.g. B17)
Number (e.g. 123456)

Last name (in Ukrainian)
First name (in Ukrainian)
Patronymic (in Ukrainian)
(Check the box if no patronymic on document)

Enter Captcha code shown above

If the authenticity of the qualification is confirmed, the following screen will appear:

Результат запити

Інформація з Реєстру документів про освіту Єдиної державної електронної бази з питань освіти щодо документа про вищу освіту

Найменування документа	Диплом спеціаліста	Diploma of Specialist	Name of the qualification
Реєстраційний номер документа в Єдиній державній електронній базі з питань освіти	BK 234	Series	Serial number
Дата видачі документа	29.06.2003	Date of issue	
Рік закінчення закладу освіти (відокремленого структурного підрозділу) (здобуття освіти)	2003	Year of Award	
Прізвище, ім'я, по батькові власника документа		Surname, name and patronymic of the holder of the qualification	
Дата народження		Date of birth	
Найменування закладу освіти (відокремленого структурного підрозділу), що закінчив (в якому здобув відповідну освіту) власник документа	Українська академія друкарства	Awarding Institution	
Кваліфікація власника документа (здобутий ступінь вищої освіти, спеціальність та, за наявності, - спеціалізація, освітня програма, професійна кваліфікація)	Здобув(ла) кваліфікацію: Ступінь вищої освіти (освітньо-кваліфікаційний рівень): Спеціалізація: Економіка підприємства Професійна кваліфікація: спеціаліста з економіки підприємства	Specialisation and professional qualification	
Найменування посади, ініціали та прізвище керівника або іншої уповноваженої особи закладу освіти - підписанта документа	Ректор Б.В. Дурняк	Rector's name	

Закрити

At present, the following educational documents are available for verification on EDEBO:

Can be verified on EDEBO

- “Plastic” diplomas from Atestat to Magister issued 1998-2014
- Custom format state-issued diploma from Atestat to Magistr issued 2015-present
- Diplomas issued to foreign students 2015-present

Can NOT be verified on EDEBO

- Diplomas issued prior to 1998
- Archival Records
- Diplomas issued by military of internal affairs institutions
- Diplomas of re-training
- Diplomas for Candidate of Science degrees
- Diplomas issued to foreign students prior to 2015
- Any other diplomas/certificates issued 1998-2014 not in plastic card format

1.2. Eliciting information on study process and educational documents by a person

EDEBO provides a publicly available service⁵⁹ for persons to check the information included in EDEBO regarding their study process and educational documents - without the need to know the requisites of these documents.

To obtain this information, a person submits a request on the EDEBO website via:

- 1 confirming his/her identity through an authorised electronic signature

ІНФОРМАЦІЯ З ЄДИНОЇ ДЕРЖАВНОЇ ЕЛЕКТРОННОЇ БАЗИ З ПИТАНЬ ОСВІТИ ЩОДО ДОКУМЕНТІВ ПРО ОСВІТУ ТА ДАНИХ ПРО НАВЧАННЯ ОСОБИ

За допомогою даного сервісу можливо отримати інформацію, що міститься в ЄДЕБО, щодо:

1) здобуття вищої освіти - з 2012 року, фахової передвищої освіти - з 2020 року, професійної (професійно-технічної) освіти - з 2013 року;

2) документів про здобуття вищу, фахову передвищу та професійну (професійно-технічну) освіту, які отримані з червня 2015 року;

3) документів про здобуття вищу, професійно-технічну та загальну середню освіту, які отримані з 2000 року, якщо на їх підставі здійснювався вступ на навчання для здобуття вищої освіти - з 2012 року, фахової передвищої освіти - з 2020 року, професійної (професійно-технічної) освіти - з 2013 року.

Інформація щодо здобуття освіти за кошти державного бюджету у вищих військових навчальних закладах (закладах вищої освіти із специфічними умовами навчання, військових навчальних підрозділах закладів вищої освіти) в ЄДЕБО не міститься.

Authorised electronic signature

Type of the authorised electronic signature

Authorised provider of electronic signature

Personal key

Signature password

Зчитування особистого ключа

Оберіть тип носія особистого ключа, особистий ключ, введіть пароль захисту ключа та натисніть "Зчитати"

Тип носія особистого ключа:

- Файловий носій (USB-flash, CD(DVD)-R(RW) тощо)
- Апаратний захищений носій КЕП
- Носій у складі сервісу

Кваліфікований надавач ел. довірчих послуг:

Визначити автоматично

Особистий ключ (Key-6.dat, *.pk, *.pk8, *.zs2 або *.jks):

Обрати

Пароль захисту ключа:

Зчитати

- 2 providing his/her full name.

Last name (in Ukrainian)

First name (in Ukrainian)

Patronymic name (in Ukrainian)

Submit the request

Instructions (in Ukrainian)

Прізвище *

Ім'я *

По батькові

Надіслати запит

Інструкція

⁵⁹ <https://info.edbo.gov.ua/check-person/>

Within several minutes after submitting the request, EDEBO automatically generates a PDF statement with all the information included in the EDEBO registers on that person, namely:

1 valid educational documents:

- Type of educational document
- Series and registration number
- Issuing educational institution
- Date of issue
- Validity period (if applicable)
- Foreign sample of the document (if applicable)
- Certificate of recognition of the document (if applicable)
- Registration number of the diploma supplement (available since 1 January 2022)

EXTRACT from the Unified State Electronic Database on Education on educational documents and information on the study process of a person					ВИПИСКА з Єдиної державної електронної бази з питань освіти щодо документів про освіту та інформації про навчання особи				
Last name, First name, Patronymic name (in Ukrainian)					Прізвище, ім'я, по батькові: [REDACTED]				
Date of birth					Дата народження: [REDACTED]				
Tax code (retrieved from authorized electronic signature)					РНОКПП (в КЕП): [REDACTED]				
Educational documents, students' (schoolchildren's) tickets					Документи про освіту, студентські (учнівські) квитки				
Type of educational document	Series	Serial number	Awarding institution	Date of issue	Validity period	Foreign document (yes/no)	Recognition certificate	Registration number of diploma supplement	
№ п/п	Тип документа	Серія	Номер	Ким видано	Дата видачі	Строк дії	Іноземний зріз	Свідчення про визнання	Реєстраційний номер додатка
1	Атестат про повну загальну середню освіту	HP	405 [REDACTED]	[REDACTED] області	27.05.2011		Ні		
2	Диплом бакалавра	B15	[REDACTED] 511	Державний вищий навчальний заклад [REDACTED]	30.06.2015		Ні		

2 valid student tickets

3 study process in educational institutions:

- Full name of the person
- Name of educational institution and its EDEBO code
- Degree
- Mode of study
- Funding source
- Programme Subject Area
- Specialization
- Study Programme
- Start and end date of study

Part 3: Verification resources to determine authenticity

EXTRACT
from the Unified State Electronic Database on Education on educational documents and information on the study process of a person

ВІПІСКА
з Єдиної державної електронної бази з питань освіти щодо документів про освіту та інформації про навчання особи

Last name, First name, Patronymic name (in Ukrainian)
Date of birth
Tax code (retrieved from authorized electronic signature)

Прізвище, ім'я, по батькові: [REDACTED]
Дата народження: [REDACTED]
РНОКПП (в КЕП): [REDACTED]

Information on the study process

Інформація про навчання

№ п/п	ПІБ	Заклад освіти (код в ЄДЕБО та назва)	Параметри навчання	Поточний статус навчання	Дата встановлення статусу
1	Супрун Катерина Миколаївна	(9) [REDACTED] університет	Освітній рівень: Бакалавр Форма навчання: Денна Фінансування: Бюджет Структурний підрозділ: [REDACTED] Спеціальність: [REDACTED] Спеціалізація: - Освітня програма: - Професія(ї): - Дати початку та закінчення навчання: 01.09.2011-30.06.2015	Завершено навчання (картка здобувача: [REDACTED])	13.07.2015

To generate the statement successfully:

- 1 a person should have his/her personal card or the taxpayer registration card number included into EDEBO, and
- 2 full name indicated in the request form and the taxpayer registration card number in the digital signature has to correspond to the ones included in the EDEBO personal card

The following information can be elicited via this service:

Type of information	Level of education	Information available since	Source of information in EDEBO
Confirmation on the person's study process	Higher education	2012	Education institutions
	Professional pre-higher education	2020	
	Vocational (technical-vocational) education	2013	
Information on the person's educational documents	Higher education, professional pre-higher education, vocational (technical-vocational) education	June 2015	Register on educational documents
Information on the person's educational documents used for enrollment into further education: higher education - since 2012, professional pre-higher education - since 2020, vocational (technical-vocational) education - since 2013)	Higher education, vocational (technical-vocational) education, comprehensive secondary education	2000	Register on educational documents

The service does not provide information on study process and educational documents for state-funded students of military higher education institutions.

2. PRINCIPAL SECURITY FEATURES OF QUALIFICATIONS

In addition to the database described above, there is another way to verify the authenticity of Ukrainian qualifications issued in the State-standard format. They are in fact equipped with so-called **security features**, or specific features useful for anti-counterfeiting initiatives which are inserted in the qualification in its original format during the production and printing phase, which, being difficult to reproduce, permit the protection of authenticity. The verification of the presence of these characteristics is normally carried out with the support of instruments such as a UV light or a microscope.

The main security features contained in Ukrainian laminated documents in plastic card format are listed below:

Colour transition

Microprint and Fine Line Pattern

Poem by T.S. Shevchenko

Laser ultraviolet protection

Left bottom corner flower absence of outline

Diploma and number microprint

Source: <http://kupit-diploma.com/uk/stepeni-zashhity-diplomov-ot-poddelok.html>

PART 4: SYNTHESIS OF INFORMATION RESOURCES

Official scholastic and higher education bodies in Ukraine

- Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine
<https://mon.gov.ua/eng>
- Ukrainian ENIC centre
<http://enic.in.ua/index.php/en/>
- National Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education
<https://en.naqqa.gov.ua>

International sources containing information updated directly by the Ukrainian authorities

- Page dedicated to Ukraine on the ENIC-NARIC website
<https://www.enic-naric.net/ukraine.aspx>
- DEQAR database – Database of External Quality Assurance Results
<https://www.eqar.eu/qa-results/search/>
- Q-Entry Database on Higher Education Entry Qualifications
<https://www.q-entry.eu/international-db/?cerca=Ukraine>

Secondary international sources created by different national/international bodies

- Database of higher education institutions of the International Association of Universities (IAU)
<https://whed.net/home.php>
- Page dedicated to the Ukrainian system on the website of the Dutch ENIC-NARIC centre (NUFFIC)
<https://www.nuffic.nl/en/education-systems/ukraine>
- Page dedicated to the Ukrainian system on the US-based World Education Services (WES) website
<https://wenr.wes.org/2019/06/education-in-ukraine>

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